

Finding AI Success in the Ocean of AI Policies, Regulations, and Standards

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1. Introduction

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes more prevalent in many societies, different, and sometimes conflicting visions of what constitutes “successful AI” have emerged. In this paper we analyse formal documents produced by supranational, standards and professional bodies from 2018-2025 which have attempted to shape visions of successful AI. This period includes early trustworthy AI guidelines through to the recent regulation setting efforts in Europe. The set of bodies includes:

- **Supranational EU and non-EU bodies:** including documents published by the EU High Level Expert Group (AI-HLEG), European Commission, United Nations (UN), UNESCO, OECD, and G7,
- **International and national technical standards bodies,** particularly ISO/IEC AI standardisation committee (Joint Technical Committee (JTC) 1/SubCommittee (SC) 42¹) and the German National Standards Body (DIN),
- **International Information and Communications Technology (ICT) professional bodies,** including ACM (Association for Computing Machinery) and IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers).

The research question we explore is: *What are the prevalent themes that indicates AI success in existing AI policies, guidelines, regulations, codes of practice, and standards published by prominent supranational, technical standardisation, and ICT professional bodies between 2018 and 2025?*

2. Methodology

Selecting Documents and Compiling the Corpus: Documents were selected for the corpus based on predefined criteria tailored to each issuing body. Overall, the corpus comprises **60 documents** published between 2018 and 2025 across three aforementioned categories of issuing bodies. Documents were selected based on their explicit focus on AI governance with no restrictions on document length or legal status. The breakdown of the type of documents are shown in Table 1.

Combining Thematic Analysis and Topic Modelling: We use a novel methodology that integrates qualitative thematic analysis [24], grounded in social sciences, with unsupervised topic modelling approaches, which are statistical methods used to identify prevalent topics in a corpus of documents. We used NVivo software² in thematic coding of subset of documents. Building upon our previous work [25], we also employed BERTopic [26] to identify topics within each document

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¹<https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

²<https://nvivo.de/en/>

Table 1: *Corpus of AI documents issued by supranational, technical standards, and ICT professional bodies*

Body	No. of docs	Included documents
Supranational bodies	13	- EU trustworthy AI guidelines published by AI-HLEG (n=4) [1, 2, 3, 4] - EU AI Act [5] and its related guidelines [6, 7, 8] (n=4) - Guidelines published by OECD [9], G20 [10], UNESCO [11], UN [12], and Council of Europe [13] (n=5)
Technical standards bodies	36	AI standards published by: - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 (n=30) - DIN (n=6)
ICT professional bodies	11	- ACM code of ethics (n=1) [14] - IEEE P7000 series (n=10) [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 16]

Figure 1: *Methodology used to identify AI success themes from AI policies, guidelines, regulations, and standards*

in the corpus. The source code and the results are available in an archived release, linked to GitHub, with a persistent digital object identifier (DOI)³, enabling reuse and reproducibility. Based on the results of manual thematic analysis and automated topic modelling, through a process of iterative interpretation of codes and topics, the **themes** were constructed, refined, and named

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18303112>

Table 2: Themes identified from *supranational bodies* (sup in red), *technical standardisation bodies* (stn in blue) and *ICT standardisation bodies* (ict in olive)

Meta-themes	Micro themes	Meso themes	Macro themes
AI Technical Features	Theme sup1: AI Technical Features Theme sup2: AI Quality Characteristics Theme stn1: AI/ML Engineering Theme stn2: Data Engineering Theme stn3: Knowledge Engineering Theme stn4: Software/System Engineering Theme ict1: Transparency Theme ict2: Operationalising Values	Theme stn5: Sectoral AI Uses	
		Theme ict3: Standards	
AI Use	Theme ict4: Use Cases	Theme sup6: Areas of AI Use	Theme sup5: Areas of AI Benefit
		Theme stn6: Horizontal AI Uses Theme ict5: Societal and Personal Impact	
AI Risks and Harms	Theme sup3: Risks addressed by organisation Theme stn7: AI Risk Sources Theme ict6: AI Safety Theme ict7: Data Concerns		
		Theme sup7: Shared Risks/Harms Theme ict8: Accountability	
	Theme stn8: Harms from AI Risks Theme stn9: AI Risk Management Techniques and Factors		
AI Governance	Theme sup4: Organisation-level governance mechanism Theme stn10: AI Governance Mechanism Theme ict9: Stakeholder Participation	Theme sup8: Sectoral/Domain Oversight Mechanisms	Theme sup9: Society-Level Governance Mechanisms Theme sup10: Society-Level Governance Principles
		Theme ict10: Human Rights Centered AI Governance Theme ict11: AI Governance Instruments	
		Theme stn11: AI Governance Factors	

through the lens of *Sociology of Expectation* [27], which allows the narratives on AI observed in different arenas to be analysed together to better understand how different stakeholder types are responding to and indeed attempting to shape dominant and largely positive narratives of the transformative nature of AI technology. Figure 1 shows the overall methodology used in this work.

3. Thematic Framework for AI Success

Drawing on the results of thematic analysis and topic modelling and inspired by knowledge engineering and qualitative data analysis methodologies, we took an inductive approach to cluster codes and topics into meaningful groups. Then, through collaborative and iterative expert interpretation, a *theme* indicating AI success criteria was assigned to each category.

The integration of codes and topics revealed 157 unique concepts across supranational body documents, 371 in technical standards, and 90 in ICT professional body documents.

These concepts were subsequently categorised into four meta-themes within each document category: **AI technical features**, **AI Uses**, **AI Risks and Harms** and **AI Governance**. Each of these was further subdivided into constituent themes within each document category. These constituent themes are also broadly categorised against a **micro-meso-macro** framing, offering a sense of where the documents expect the issues to be best governed:

- **Micro themes:** expectations are attended to by individual or-

ganisations, but they may do so in ways different to other organisations.

- **Meso themes:** expectations are attended to at a specific sectoral or national policy level.
- **Macro themes:** expectations are attended to at a supranational level and expected to span sectoral or policy domains.

Table 2 demonstrates the themes identified from each document category using the following colour coding. The identified themes signal the emergence of a *multiscalar AI governance system*, with the following key findings across each category:

- EU policy documents reflect an evolution from *AI ethical principles* to *regulatory compliance*.
- Non-EU supranational bodies emphasise human rights and diversity and inclusion, while EU’s focus is on individual and social risks, brining “fundamental rights” into fore.
- Technical standardisation bodies place strong expectations on organisations to implement technical measures for risk management and AI governance, though fragmentation persists around ethical, social, and environmental issues.
- ICT professional bodies direct the expectation of success toward individual AI researchers and professional, as the primary actors responsible for ethical AI.

In future work, we aim to systematically compare the themes identified across all three document categories to uncover overlaps, divergences, and gaps in expectations of AI. Building on these findings, we further intend to develop a comprehensive taxonomy of AI success indicators.

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